

A Faunistic Study of Pentatomidae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) from Çankırı Province of Türkiye

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ABSTRACT: This study is based on 430 Pentatomidae materials collected from Çankırı in Türkiye between 2013-2014. In this study, 30 species/subspecies were determined. After 76 years, a new locality record of *Anthemina varicornis* (Jakovlev, 1874) is given from Türkiye. The study includes information about the distribution data of Pentatomid species and newly recorded species of Çankırı province given. With this study, additional distribution information was provided to the Turkish Pentatomidae fauna

KEYWORDS: Heteroptera, Pentatomidae, New records of Çankırı (Province), Turkish Fauna.

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INTRODUCTION

The pentatomids are known as Stink Bugs or Shield Bugs. They are frequently found in large numbers on crops and weeds.

If disturbed, they will emit a pungent, evil-smelling liquid. They are mostly brown, some are greenish, although a few are highly colored.

Stink bugs are distinguished from other bugs by their 3rd thorax, or the triangular scutum, which is well extended to cover half of their back, but not covered the whole abdomen. Most of the Stink Bug species are plant suckers although some are predators to other insects. Some species in this family exhibit maternal care by standing guard over their egg batches. All Stink Bugs are active during the day (Rider, 2002). The family Pentatomidae is one of the 7 families of the Pentatomoidea superfamily in Türkiye (Önder et al., 2006). More than 45,000 species are known worldwide, and over 9,365 species belonging to 1,632 genera are distributed in the Palearctic Region (Aukema et al., 2013; Henry, 2017). Pentatomidae has 940 genera and 4,949 species belonging to 10 subfamilies worldwide, and 219 genera, 841 species and 19 subspecies belonging to 4 subfamilies in the Palearctic Region (Rider, 2006; Henry, 2017; Rider et al., 2018). In Türkiye, it includes 61 genera, 174 species/ subspecies belonging to 4 subfamilies (Fent & Dursun, 2022).

Çankırı is located between the Central Anatolian region and the Black Sea region and therefore contains the character-

istics of both and constitutes a transition area. The lands of this province are shared between the Western Black Sea and the Central Kızılırmak Section of the Central Anatolian region. Especially this province and its surroundings were not studied, and data were created based on the samples collected during the trips. Ilgaz Mountains are the only region that has been specially studied in terms of Pentatomidae fauna of Çankırı province (Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015). The aim of this study is to determine Pentatomidae fauna of Çankırı and to make a contribution to Turkish Pentatomidae fauna.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study is based on 430 specimens of Pentatomidae and all the specimens were collected by the first author from Çankırı 2013 and 2014. As a result of identification, 30 species/subspecies for the family Pentatomidae were determined. Samples were collected from the host plants. Collected samples were taken into prepared kill bottles containing 70% alcohol and killed. The available specimens for the present study are deposited in Nazife Tuatay Plant Protection Museum, Ankara, Türkiye (NTM).

RESULTS

In this study, 30 species, /subspecies and 3 subfamilies belonging to the Pentatomidae family from Türkiye are included. The species are given below.

Family: Pentatomidae Leach, 1815

Subfamily: Asopinae Spinola, 1850

***Picromerus bidens* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Çerkeş, Dağçukurören village, 40°44'32"N, 32°50'17"E, 1271 m, 29.VIII.2013, ♂.

Chorotype: Holarctic.

Previous records: Ankara, Artvin, Çanakkale, Çorum, Giresun, Isparta, Kırklareli, Nevşehir, Ordu, Tekirdağ (Lodos et al., 1978; Lodos & Önder 1983; Kıyak, 1993; Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Japoshvili 2012; Orçan & Kıvanç, 2017; Fent & Dursun 2022).

***Zicrona caerulea* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: 2. km from Çankırı exit to Yapraklı, 40°35'57"N, 33°37'12"E, 730 m, 23.VII.2013, ♀; Ilgaz, Between Alıç village and Osman Plateau, 40°59'46,3"N, 33°30'45,8"E, 1504 m, 18.VII.2014, ♀, ♂.

Chorotype: Palearctic.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Ağrı, Ankara, Artvin, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bolu, Çankırı, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hakkâri, Hatay, Iğdır, İzmir, Kırklareli, Kilis, Konya, Mersin, Samsun, Siirt, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Zonguldak (Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1978, 1987; Lodos & Önder, 1983; Önder et al., 2006; Külekçi et al., 2009; Orçan & Kıvanç, 2017; Çerçi & Gözüaçık, 2019; Fent & Dursun 2022).

Subfamily: Pentatominae Leach, 1815

***Aelia acuminata* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Atkaracalar, Budak village entry, 40°51'05"N, 33°8'37"E, 1250 m, 25.VIII.2013, ♂, Between Budakpınarı village and Yakalı village, 40°53'26"N, 33°8'58"E, 1314 m, 25.VIII.2013, ♂, Yakalı village entrance, 40°53'56"N, 33°8'51"E, 1210 m, 25.VIII.2013, ♀, 2 ♂♂; Bayramören, Boğazkaya, 40°59'26,7"N, 33°17'13"E, 1019 m, 19. VII.2014, ♀; Centre, İnanç village, 40°38'1"N, 33°40'30"E, 761 m, 24.VII.2013, ♀, Between Eldivan Exit-Çankırı 2.km, 40°34'23"N, 33°30'42"E, 857 m, 26.IV.2014, 3 ♀♀, Salt Cave location, 40°31'38"N, 33°45'55"E, 699 m, 26.IV.2014, ♀; Çerkeş, On the road between Kadiözü- Aliözü villages, 40°49'26"N, 32°57'49"E, 1257 m, 26.VIII.2013, 2 ♂♂, Between Cedime, Çalcıören, Coroğlu villages turn and Kabak village, 40°53'19"N, 32°54'47"E, 1557 m, 27.VIII. 2013, ♀, Between Avşar İncügez, 40°54'14,8"N, 33°00'42,5"E, 1476 m, 10.VIII.2014, ♀, Doğdu village, 40°53'15,4"N, 32°55'01,3"E, 1559 m, 19.VIII.2014, ♀, Akbaşla-Korakoca return, 40°54'55,9"N, 32°53'04,4"E, 912 m, 21.VIII.2014, 3 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂; Bayramören, Between Pirinçli and Sazak village, 40°58'20"N, 33°4'47"E, 1630 m, 27.VIII.2013, ♀, Kadılar Plateau, 40°49'38"N, 32°37'57"E, 1154 m, 28.VIII.2013, ♀; Kızılırmak, Bostanlı entrance, 40°19'43,6"N, 33°49'08"E, 573 m, 12.VII.2014, ♀, 4 km before the village of Cacıklar, 40°23'43"N, 34°04'18"E, 597 m, 24.IV.2014, ♂, Between Kenallı and Halaçlı, 40°18'51,2"N, 33°59'12"E, 565 m, 12.VIII.2014, ♀; Orta, Elden Plateau, 40°39'13"N, 32°57'07"E, 1487 m, 21.V.2014, ♀, 2 ♂♂, Kurşunlu, Köpürlü entrance, 40°47'12,5"N, 33°16'49,7"E, 1006 m, 10.VII.2014, ♀, Dodurga Plateau, 40°37'12,2"N, 32°59'34,3"E, 1390 m, 10.VII.2014, ♂; Eldivan, Center entrance, 40°32'23"N, 33°30'15,7"E, 931 m, 11.VII.2014, ♀; Ilgaz, Sarmaşık village, 40°48'7"N, 33°39'55"E, 1687 m, 25.VII.2013, ♀, Bozan entry, 40°54'34"N, 33°36'16"E, 867 m, 26.VII.2013, ♀; Ilgaz, Kale village, 40°57'12,3"N, 33°39'12,2" E, 980 m, 17.VII.2014, ♂, Between Yenidemirciler and Süleyman Hancılar, 40°54'48,2"N, 33°30'13,7"E, 983 m, 19.VII.2014, ♀; Şabanözü, Demirsahan village turnout, 40°25'43,6"N, 33°17'38,1"E, 1035 m, 08.VIII.2014, ♂, Gümedğin village, 40°26'19,3"N, 33°15'43,9"E, 1032 m, 08.VIII.2014, ♂.

Chorotype: Palearctic.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Afyon, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bayburt, Burdur, Bilecik, Bolu, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Edirne, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hatay, Iğdır, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kırklareli, Kırşehir, Kocaeli, Konya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Niğde, Ordu, Osmaniye, Rize, Sakarya, Samsun, Sinop, Siirt, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Şırnak, Tekirdağ, Trabzon, Tokat, Tunceli, Uşak, Zonguldak (Puton, 1892; Horváth, 1901; Fahringer, 1922; Hoberlandt, 1956; Linnavuori, 1965; Awal, 1977; Lodos et al., 1978, 1982; 1987; 1998; Önder et al., 1995, 2006; Fent, & Aktaç, 1999; Kıyak, 2000; Öz Saraç et al., 2001; Öz Saraç & Kıyak 2001; Dursun, 2004; Kıyak et al., 2004; Özgen et al., 2005; Dursun & Kartal, 2008c; Külekçi et al., 2009; Abacıgil et al., 2010; Şerban., 2010; Fent, 2010, 2011; Dursun & Fent., 2011; Gözüaçık et al., 2011; Tezcan et al., 2013; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Dirik & Kıvanç, 2016; Orçan & Kıvanç, 2017; Çerçi & Gözüaçık, 2019; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

***Aelia rostrata* Boheman, 1852**

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Centre, between Pehlivanlı and Alaçatı villages, 40°34'19"N, 33°52'18"E, 925 m, 26.IV.2014, 4 ♀♀, ♂, between Bayındır and Hasakça, 40°35'16,4"N, 33°49'10,7"E, 1104 m, 13.VIII.2014, ♀, ♂, Dutağaç village, 40°41'25"N, 33°48'56"E, 1030 m, 24.VII.2013, ♂, Salt Cave location, 40°31'38"N, 33°45'55"E, 699 m, 26.IV.2014, ♀, ♂; Çerkeş, between Avşar-İncügez, 40°54'14,8"N, 33°00'42,5"E, 1476 m, 10.VIII.2014, ♀, On the road between Kadıözü- Aliözü villages, 40°49'26"N, 32°57'49"E, 1257 m 26.VIII.2013, ♀; between Yıprak- Tohumlar villages, 40°55'1"N, 32°48'34"E, 1153 m 26.VIII.2013, ♂; Kızılırmak, Aşağıalagöz village entrance, 40°22'28"N, 33°54'54"E, 619 m, 24.IV.2014, 2 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂; Ilgaz, Belören, 40°52'11"N, 33°29'39"E, 1543 m, 25.VII.2013, ♀, ♂, Kaleköyü, 40°57'12,3"N, 33°39'12,2"E, 980 m, 17.VII.2014, ♀, Karamursel village turnout, 40°26'18"N, 34°01'19"E, 550 m 24.IV.2014, ♂, between Boyacıoğlu-Karamürsel, 40°25'36"N, 34°02'19"E, 543 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀, Karamursel village exit, Halimintepe, 40°24'06"N, 34°02'26"E, 550 m, 24.IV.2014, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂, Kemalli village entrance, 40°18'6"N, 34°02'37"E, 686 m, 24.IV.2014, ♂, between Kemalli and Halaçlı villages, 40°18'7"N, 33°58'33"E, 608 m 24.IV.2014, ♀; Korgun, between Bugay and Ildızım, 40°42'27"N, 33°29'23"E, 909 m, 23.V.2014, 2 ♀♀, ♂, Maruf village exit, 40°38'18"N, 33°26'22"E, 1181 m, 20.V.2014, 2 ♀♀, Yukarıçavuş village, 40°42'22"N, 33°38'59"E, 940 m, 21.IV.2013, ♀, Kurşunlu, between Sürürlü and Sakaeli, 40°42'01"N, 33°08'53"E, 1415 m, 21.V.2014, ♀, ♂, Dumanlı village exit, 40°40'31"N, 33°13'45"E, 1403 m, 20.V.2014, ♀; Orta, Dodurga entrance, 40°36'11"N, 33°00'18"E, 1351 m, 22.V.2014, ♂, Sakaeli exit, 40°40'19"N, 33°09'48"E, 1227 m, 21.V.2014, ♀, Sakarcaören village entrance, 40°37'16"N, 33°08'46"E, 1305 m, 20.V.2014, ♀, Yuva village exit, 40°36'57"N, 33°01'36"E, 1306 m, 22.V.2014, ♂; Şabanözü, Büyükyakalı village entrance, 40°28'38"N, 33°14'25"E, 1091 m, 23.V.2014, ♂; Yapraklı, Between Buluca and Iğdır, 40°45'32"N, 33°46'58,7"E, 1172 m, 15.VII.2014, ♀.

Chorotype: European.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Afyonkarahisar, Aksaray, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bilecik, Bolu, Burdur, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Kırklareli, Kırşehir, Konya, Kocaeli, Kütahya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Muş, Nevşehir, Niğde, Ordu, Sakarya, Samsun, Siirt, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Şırnak, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Tunceli, Uşak, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Puton & Noualhier, 1895; Escherich, 1897; Horváth, 1903a as *A. syriaca*; Kiritshenko, 1918; Fahringer, 1922; Kiritshenko, 1924; Hoberlandt, 1956; Wagner, 1959; Awel, 1977; Lodos et al., 1978, 1998; Önder et al., 1995 as *A. syriaca*, 2006; Kıvan, 1998; Fent & Aktaç, 1999; Kıyak, 2000; Özsarac & Kıyak, 2001; Özsarac et al., 2001; Özgen et al., 2005a; Dursun & Kartal, 2008c; Külekçi et al., 2009; Fent, 2010; Dursun & Fent, 2011a; Gözüaçık et al., 2011; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Tezcan et al., 2013; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Dirik & Kıvan, 2016; Çerçi & Gözüaçık, 2019; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

***Anthemina pusio pusio* (Kolenati, 1846)**

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Centre, between Ovacık village- Kuzuköy, 40°32'28"N, 33°52'12"E, 920 m, 26.IV.2014, ♀; Kızılırmak, Kuzey kışla village entrance, 40°22'14"N, 34°03'00"E, 600 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀, Karamürsel village exit Halimintepe, 40°24'06"N, 34°02'26"E, 550 m, 24.IV.2014, ♂.

Chorotype: Turanian.

Previous records: Elazığ (Önder et al., 2006).

***Anthemina varicornis* (Jakovlev, 1874)**

Material examined: **Çankırı Prov.:** Centre, Balıbağı Plateau, 40°29'50"N, 33°52'42"E, 774 m, 25.IV.2014, ♀; Kızılırmak, Kuzeykişla village entrance, 40°22'14"N, 34°03'00"E, 600 m, 24.IV.2014, ♂;

Chorotype: Euro-Mediterranean.

Previous records: Ankara, Bursa (Hoberlandt, 1956 as *Dolycoris varicornis*).

***Apodiphus amygdali* (Germar, 1817)**

Material examined: **Çankırı Prov.:** Kızılırmak, between Kemalli-Halaçlı villages, 40°18'7"N, 33°58'33"E, 608 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀.

Chorotype: Southwest Asiatic.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bingöl, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İçel, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Kars, Kayseri, Kilis, Konya, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Osmaniye, Rize, Şanlıurfa, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Tunceli (Horváth, 1883; Puton & Noualhier, 1895; Kiritshenko, 1918; Fahringer, 1922; Hoberlandt, 1956; Ghauri, 1977; Lodos et al., 1978, 1998; Önder & Adıgüzel, 1979; Önder et al., 1983, 1995; Kıyak, 1990; Derjanschi & Péricart, 2005; Özgen et al., 2005a; Bolu et al., 2006; Fent & Aktaç, 2008; Dursun & Kartal, 2008a; Karsavuran et al., 2008; Külekçi et al., 2009; Fent, 2010; Fent et al., 2010; Şerban, 2010; Tezcan et al., 2010; Dursun & Fent, 2011a; Gözüaçık et al., 2011; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Kaçar & Dursun, 2015; Çerçi et al., 2018; Çerçi & Gözüaçık, 2019; Bulak & Yıldırım, 2021; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

***Codophila varia* (Fabricius, 1787)**

Material examined: **Çankırı Prov.:** Centre, Balıbağı, 40°29'50"N, 33°52'42"E; 774 m; 25. IV.2014, ♂, Danabaşı Village, 40°31'33"N, 34°02'46"E, 724 m, 26.IV.2014, 2 ♀, Ovacık village-Kuzu village entrance, 40°32'28"N, 33°52'12"E, 920 m, 26. IV.2014, ♀; Kızılırmak, Cacıklar Village 4 Km left 40°23'43"N, 34°04'18"E, 597 m, 24.IV.2014, 2 ♀♀, Karamürsel Village exit, Halimin tepe 40°24'06"N, 34°02'26"E, 550 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀, ♂, Kuzeykişla Village entrance, 40°22'14"N, 34°03'00"E, 600 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀, ♂; Şabanözü, Demirsahan Village exit, 40°24'58,7"N, 33°18'58"E, 906 m, 08.VIII.2014, ♀.

Chorotype: Turano Mediterranean.

Previous records: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın Balıkesir, Bilecik, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Eskişehir, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hakkâri, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İçel, İstanbul, İzmir Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırklareli, Kırşehir, Kilis, Kocaeli, Konya, Kütahya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Samsun, Siirt, Sinop, Sivas, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Tunceli Zonguldak (Puton, 1892; Kiritshenko, 1918; Fahringer, 1922; Linnavuori, 1954; Hoberlandt, 1956; Wagner, 1959, 1966; Lodos et al., 1978, 1998; Önder et al., 1983, 1995; Kıyak, 1990, 1993, 2016; Fent, & Aktaç, 1999; Awad, 2000; Öz Saraç & Kıyak, 2001; Öz Saraç et al., 2001; Kıyak et al., 2004; Dursun & Kartal, 2008b; Karsavuran et al., 2008; Külekçi et al., 2009; Fent, 2010; Şerban, 2010; Dursun & Fent, 2011a; Tezcan et al., 2013; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Çerçi et al., 2018; Çerçi & Gözüaçık, 2019; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

***Dolycoris baccarum* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: **Çankırı Prov.:** Atkaracalar, Ilıpınar village exit, 40°48'10,8"N, 33°05'57,4"E, 1169 m, 20.VIII.2014, ♂, Yakalı village entrance, 40°53'56"N, 33°8'51"E, 1210 m, 25.VIII.2013, ♀, Budakpınar entrance, 40°51'07"N, 33°08'38"E,

1210 m, 19.VIII.2014, ♂, Demirli-Höyük girişi 40°50'06"N, 33°03'44"E, 1275 m, 19.VIII.2014, ♀; Bayramören, between Çayırçık and Evkadı village, 41°2'8"N, 33°9'28"E, 1000 m, 27.VIII.2013, ♂, Karaduk village entrance, 40°59'17,9"N, 33°03'43,0"E, 1302 m, 21.VIII.2014, ♂, Harmancik village exit, 41°03'17,6"N, 33°12'31,0"E, 639 m, 19.VII.2014, ♂, Centre, Aşağıçavuş village, 40°41'39,7"N, 33°38'01,7"E, 880 m, 15.VII.2014, ♀, Balıbağı plataeu, 40°29'50"N, 33°52'42"E, 774 m, 25.IV.2014, 3 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂, between Başegmez and Alanpınar, 40°43'52,4"N, 33°36'37,7"E, 956 m, 09.VIII.2014, ♂, between Kuzukoy and Agzibuyuk village, 40°30'25"N, 33°59'01"E, 617 m, 26.IV.2014, ♀; Centre, Çayırpınar plataeu, 40°28'34"N, 33°54'09"E, 726 m, 25.IV.2014, 2 ♀♀, Danabaşı village, 40°31'33"N, 34°02'46"E, 724 m, 26.IV.2014, ♂, Eldivan exit - 2 km from Çankırı, 40°34'23"N, 33°30'42"E, 857 m, 26.IV.2014, 4 ♀♀, 8 ♂♂, İnanç village, 40°38'1"N, 33°40'30"E, 761 m, 24.VII.2013, ♀; Çerkeş, between Avşar İncüğez, 40°54'14,8"N, 33°00'42,5"E, 1476 m, 10.VIII.2014, 2 ♀♀, between Dere plateau-Suluk plateau, 40°42'44 "N, 32°52'56"E, 1422 m, 29.VIII.2013, ♀, between Örenköy and Yakuplar, 40°45'02,9"N, 32°52'21,6"E, 1257 m, 20.VIII.2014, ♀, between Yahözü-Hacılar, 40°44'32,1"N, 32°52'03,9"E, 1217 m, 20.VIII.2014, ♂, between Yeşilören Village and E5 highway, 40°49'38"N, 32°37'57"E, 1154 m, 28.VIII.2013, ♀, between Yörökköy and Karakoca village, 40°54'34,7" N, 32°5'40,3"E, 923 m, 20.VII.2014, ♂, Forest area beyond Yeşilören villa-ge, 40°47'32"N, 32°35'12"E, 1597 m, 28.VIII.2013, 2 ♂♂; Provincial borders of Çankırı, Bolu and Ankara, 40°46'46"N, 32°34'19"E, 1709 m, 28.VIII.2013, ♀, Ova entrance, 40°47'27,6"N, 32°57'25,7"E, 1148 m, 20.VIII.2014, ♀, Yoncalı village return, 40°42'13"N, 32°46'26"E, 1314 m, 27.VII.2013, ♂; Eldivan, 2. Km between Akçalı-Çiftlikköy, 40°35'54"N, 33°29' 25"E, 1039 m, 23.IV.2013, ♀, 40°32'25"N, 33°30'18"E, 922 m, 23.IV.2013, 2 ♀♀, Eldivan Mountain, 40°30'24,5"N, 33°30'28"E, 1132 m, 11.VII.2014, 3 ♀♀, Return to Seydiköy, 40°34'02,5"N, 33°28'57,7"E, 891 m, 09.VII.2014, ♀; Ilgaz, between Beyköy and Saraycık, 40°59'46,3"N, 33°45'37,4"E, 1211 m, 17.VII.2014, ♂, between Yenidemirciler and Süleyman Hancılar, 40°54'48,2"N, 33°30'13,7"E, 983 m, 19.VII.2014, ♂, Ilgaz, Ilgaz exit-Gircen 40°54'55"N, 33°37'41"E, 887 m, 22.IV.2013, ♂, Kırkpınar Plataeu, 40°58'54,5"N, 33°35'0,9"E, 1435 m, 24.VIII.2014, ♂, Yaylaören village distinction, 40°52'42"N, 33°30'31"E, 914 m, 22.IV.2013, 4 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; Kızılırmak, 4 km from Cacıklar village, 40°23'43"N, 34°04'18"E, 597 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀, Asagiovacik village entrance, 40°26'29"N, 33°53'27"E, 576 m 25.IV.2014, ♀, 2 ♂♂, Bostanlı entrance, 40°19'43,6"N, 33°49'08"E, 573 m, 12.VII.2014, ♀, Karamursel village turnout, 40°26'18"N, 34°01'19"E, 550 m, 24.IV.2014, 2 ♂♂, Kenallı-Halaçlı arası, 40°18'51,2"N, 33°59'12"E, 565 m, 12.VIII.2014, ♀, ♂, Kuzeykışla village entrance, 40°22'14"N, 34°03'00"E, 600 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀, ♂, Return to Karallı village 2. Km, 40°18'30"N, 33°56'36"E, 606 m, 25.IV.2014, ♀, Saraycık village turn, 40°20'01"N, 33°58'29"E, 565 m, 25.IV.2014, 3 ♀♀, Tepealagöz Village exit, 40°21'49"N, 34°00'56"E, 557 m, 24.IV.2014, 2 ♀♀; Korgun, Akçavakıf, 40°41'35,5"N, 33°34'18,2"E, 824 m, 15.VII.2014, ♀, Akçavakıf, 40°41'40"N, 33°33'37"E, 826 m, 22.IV.2013, ♀, Aşağıçavuş village on the Çankırı-Korgun road, 40°41'08"N, 33°36'41"E, 837 m, 21.IV.2013, ♂, Between Karatekin and Yolkaya villages, 40°41'30"N, 33°29'20"E, 957 m, 22.IV.2013, 5 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂, Bugay village, 40°43'15"N, 33°30'51"E, 864 m, 23.VII.2013, ♀, Kayaçivi, 40°41'47,3"N, 33°27'43,5"E, 1005 m, 07.VIII.2014, ♀, Maruf exit, 40°38'25"N, 33°26'02"E, 1200m, 23.V.2014, 5 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂, Maruf village exit, 40°38'18"N, 33°26'22"E, 1181 m, 20.V.2014, ♂, Sanı Plataeu, 40°37'00"N, 33°24'10"E, 1363 m, 20.V.2014, ♀; Kurşunlu, between Köprülü and Kapaklı, 40°45'11"N, 33°16'31"E, 1329 m, 20.V.2014, ♀, Bridge return, 40°50'29"N, 33°15'38"E, 1130 m, 20.V.2014, ♀, Kö-pürlü exit, 40°46'41,1"N, 33°16'57,9"E, 1068 m, 06.VIII.2014, ♀, ♂; Orta, Doğanlar Village exit, 40°39'09"N, 33°10'18"E, 1315 m, 20.V.2014, ♀, between Elmalı and Kayı-lar, 40°32'14"N, 33°06'35,4"E, 1370 m, 08.VII.2014, ♂, Çerkeş, Hacılar, 40°42'34"N,

32°58'42"E, 1277 m, 21.V.2014, ♀, Dodurga entrance, 40°36'11"N, 33°00'18"E, 1351 m, 22.V.2014, ♀, Hasanlıca Plateau, 40°34'14,2"N, 33°1'26,4"E, 1336 m, 06.VIII.2014, ♀, Sakaeli exit, 40°40'19"N, 33°09'48"E, 1227 m, 21.V.2014, ♀, Sakarcören village entrance, 40°37'16"N, 33°08'46"E, 1305 m, 20.V.2014, ♀, Yuva village exit, 40°36'57"N, 33°01'36"E, 1306 m, 22.V.2014, 5 ♀♀; Şabanözü, Bakırlı village, 40°28'00"N, 33°22'27"E, 1028 m, 24.V.2014, ♀, Demirsahan village exit, 40°24'58,7"N, 33°18'58"E, 906 m, 08.VIII.2014, ♂, Mart village entrance, 40°25'16"N, 33°22'00"E, 910 m, 24.V.2014, ♂; Yapraklı, Tatlıpınar return, 40°43'0,07"N, 33°52'02,4"E, 915 m, 25.VIII.2014, ♂, Yukarıöz Great Plateau road, 40°45'40,9"N, 33°48'44,1"E, 1289 m, 15.VII.2014, ♀.

Chorotype: Palearctic.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Afyon, Ağrı, Aksaray, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Ardahan, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Batman, Bayburt, Bilecik, Burdur, Bursa, Bolu, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Giresun, Hatay, Hakkâri, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Kirklareli, Kilis, Kocaeli, Konya, Kütahya, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Muş, Nevşehir, Niğde, Ordu, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Samsun, Siirt, Sinop, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Şırnak, Tekirdağ, Trabzon, Tokat, Tunceli, Uşak, Zonguldak (Puton, 1892; Escherich, 1897; Horváth, 1901, 1905, 1919; Kiritshenko, 1918, 1924; Fahringer, 1922; Gadeau de Kerville, 1939; Hoberlandt, 1956; Wagner, 1959; Linnavuori, 1965; Wagner, 1966; Lodos et al., 1978; Önder et al., 1981, 2006; Kıyak, 1990; Önder et al., 1995; Kıvan, 1998; Lodos et al., 1998; Fent, & Aktaç, 1999; Awad, 2000; Kıyak, 2000; Öz Saraç et al., 2001; Öz Saraç & Kıyak, 2001; Bolu, 2002; Kıyak et al., 2004; Özgen et al., 2005a, b; Bolu et al., 2006; Dursun & Kartal, 2008a; Karşavuran et al., 2008; Demirel, 2009; Külekçi et al., 2009; Şerban, 2010; Tezcan et al., 2010; Fent, 2010, 2011; Dursun & Fent, 2011a; Fent, Gözüaçık et al., 2011; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Tezcan et al., 2013; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Yıldırım et al., 2014; Kaçar & Dursun, 2015; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Dirik & Kıvan, 2016; Kıyak, 2016; Orçan & Kıvan, 2017; Çerçi et al., 2018; Çerçi & Gözüaçık, 2019; Tolga & Yoldaş, 2019; Bulak & Yıldırım, 2021; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Yazıcı, 2022; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

***Eurydema (Eurydema) oleracea* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Bayramören, Çakırbağ Entrance, 40°58'17,3"N, 33°04'01,0"E, 1457 m, 21.VIII.2014, ♂; Center, Between Eldivan Exit-Çankırı 2. Km, 40°34'23"N, 33°30'42"E, 857 m, 26.IV.2014, ♂; Çerkeş, Between Yörük and Karakoca village, 40°54'34,7"N, 32°5'40,3"E, 923 m, 20.VII.2014, ♂; Ilgaz, Belsöğüt Village Exit, 40°56'51,6"N, 33°36'13"E, 1019 m, 17.VII.2014, 2 ♀♀, Eskikıymık köy entry, 41°0'19"N, 33°41'15"E, 1230 m, 26.VII.2013, ♀; Kızılırmak, Bozkır Village Entrance, 40°26'54,3"N, 33°49'25"E, 1637 m, 11.VIII.2014, ♂; Korgun, Akçavakıf, 40°41'35,5"N, 33°34'18,2"E, 824 m, 15.VII.2014, ♂, Maruf exit, 40°38'25"N, 33°26'02"E, 1200 m, 23.V.2014, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂, Maruf Village Exit, 40°38'18"N, 33°26'22"E, 1181 m, 20.V.2014, ♂, 3 ♀♀, Sanı Plateau, 40°37'00"N, 33°24'10"E, 1363 m, 20.V.2014, ♂; Kurşunlu, Between Sünürlü-Sakaeli, 40°42'01"N, 33°08'53"E, 1415 m, 21.V.2014, ♂, ♀, Dumanlı Village Exit, 40°40'31"N, 33°13'45"E, 1403 m, 20.V.2014, ♂; Orta, Buğdüz Village exit, 40°36'5,4"N, 33°3'3,7"E, 1314 m, 06.VIII.2014, ♂, Çerkeş Hacılar, 40°42'34"N, 32°58'42"E, 1277 m, 21.V.2014, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂, Derebayındır Village exit, 40°34'41"N, 32°59'36,1"E, 1364 m, 06.VIII.2014, ♂, 2 ♀♀, Elden Plateau, 40°39'13"N, 32°57'07"E, 1487 m, 21.V.2014, 4 ♂♂, 9 ♀♀, Elmalı Entrance, 40°32'47,9"N, 33°9'7,9"E, 1280 m, 07.VIII.2014, ♀, İncecik Village Entrance, 40°35'33"N, 32°55'59"E, 1600 m, 22.V.2014, ♀, İnkılap Village, 40°34'48"N, 33°03'41"E, 1290 m, 24.V.2014, ♂, ♀, Kayıören Return 2. Km, 40°34'21"N,

32°57'52"E, 1602 m, 22.V.2014, ♂, Kırşakal Village, 40°38'59"N, 33°08'17"E, 1238 m, 20.V.2014, ♂, Sakarcaören Village Exit, 40°37'16"N, 33°08'46"E, 1305 m, 20.V.2014, ♀, Yuva Village Exit, 40°36'57"N, 33°01'36"E, 1306 m, 22.V.2014, ♂, ♀; Yapraklı, Aşağıöz Return, 40°48'26,1"N, 33°54'41,6"E, 1144 m, 25.VIII.2014, ♀.

Chorotype: Sibero-European.

Previous records: Adana, Afyon, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Ardahan, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bolu, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Düzce, Edirne, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hatay, Isparta, Iğdır, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kars, Kastamonu, Kırklareli, Kocaeli, Konya, Kütahya, Manisa, Mersin, Niğde, Ordu, Osmaniye, Rize, Samsun, Sakarya, Sinop, Tekirdağ, Trabzon, Tunceli, Tokat, Uşak, Zonguldak, Yalova (Horváth, 1883; Puton 1892; Escherich, 1897; Kiritshenko, 1918; Fahringer, 1922; Kiritshenko, 1924; Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1978, 1998; Kıyak, 1993; Önder et al., 1995, 2006; Fent & Aktaç, 1999; Özşaraç et al., 2001; Dursun & Kartal, 2008b; Dursun & Kartal, 2008c; Külekçi et al., 2009; Fent, 2010, 2011; Dursun & Fent, 2011b; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Yıldırım et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Çerçi & Gözüaçık, 2019; Koca & Koca, 2020; Yazıcı, 2022; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

Eurydema (Eurydema) ornata (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined: **Çankırı Prov.:** Atkaracalar, Yakalı Village Entrance, 40°53'56"N, 33°8'51"E, 1210 m, 25.VIII.2013, ♂, ♀; Center, Balıbağı Plateau, 40°29'50"N, 33°52'42"E, 774 m, 25.IV.2014, ♂; Eldivan, 2. km between Akçalı-Çiftlik village, 40°35'54"N, 33°29'25"E, 1039 m, 23.IV.2013, ♂, Eldivan entry, 40°32'25"N, 33°30'18"E, 922 m, 23.IV.2013, 4 ♀♀; Kızılırmak, Kuzeykişla village entrance, 40°22'14"N, 34°03'00"E, 600 m, 24.IV.2014, ♂, 2 ♀♀; Korgun, Korgun entry, 40°44'8"N, 33°29'19"E, 999 m, 23.IV.2013, ♀, Maruf exit, 40°38'25"N, 33°26'02"E, 1200 m, 23.V.2014, ♂, 3 ♀♀, Maruf Village Exit, 40°38'18"N, 33°26'22"E, 1181 m, 20.V.2014, ♀; Kurşunlu, Between Köprülü-Kapaklı, 40°45'11"N, 33°16'31"E, 1329 m, 20.V.2014, ♂, 3 ♀♀, Kursunlu exit 5. Km, near Devrez Stream, 40°48'53"N, 33°17'28"E, 1126 m, 23.IV.2013, ♀; Orta, Elden Plateau, 40°39'13"N, 32°57'07"E, 1487 m, 21.V.2014, ♀, İnkılap Village, 40°34'48"N, 33°03'41"E, 1290 m, 24.V.2014, ♀, Yuva Village Exit, 40°36'57"N, 33°01'36"E, 1306 m, 22.V.2014, ♂.

Chorotype: Palearctic.

Previous records: Adana, Adapazarı, Adıyaman, Afyonkarahisar, Ağrı, Aksaray, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Batman, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bitlis, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hakkâri, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İçel, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Kırklareli, Kilis, Kocaeli, Konya, Kütahya, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Samsun, Sinop, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Şırnak, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Trabzon, Tunceli, Uşak, Yalova, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883, 1901, 1918, 1919, Puton & Noualhier, 1895; Escherich, 1897; Fahringer, 1922; Gadeau de Kerville, 1939, Hoberlandt, 1956; Wagner, 1959, 1966; Linnavuori, 1965; Lodos et al., 1978, 1998; Kıyak 1990, 1993, 2000; Önder et al., 1983, 1984, 1995, Yılmaz, 1996, Fent & Aktaç, 1999; Özşaraç & Kıyak, 2001; Özşaraç et al., 2001; Kıyak et al., 2004; Özgen et al., 2005a, b; Dursun & Kartal, 2008c; Karsavuran et al., 2008, Demirel, 2009; Külekçi et al., 2009; Fent, 2010; Şerban, 2010; Dursun & Fent, 2011b; Gözüaçık et al., 2011; Tezcan et al., 2013; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Orçan & Kıvanç, 2017; Çerçi et al., 2018; Çerçi & Gözüaçık, 2019; Bulak & Yıldırım, 2021; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Fent, & Dursun, 2022).

Eurydema (Horvatheurydema) fieberi Schummel, 1837

Material examined: **Çankırı Prov.:** Center, Tuz Cave Location, 40°31'38"N, 33°45'55"E, 699 m, 26.IV.2014, ♀.

Chorotype: Turano Mediterranean.

Previous records: Adana, Siirt (Horváth, 1901 as *E. fieberi* var. *armanicum*, Derjanschi & Péricart 2005), Bursa (Horváth, 1901, as *E. fieberi* var. *caucasicum*), Batman, Diyarbakır (Wagner, 1959 as *E. armanicum*), Adana, Adıyaman, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Bayburt, Bingöl, Burdur, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Giresun, Hakkâri, Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kırşehir, Kilis, Konya, Kütahya, Malatya, Mardin, Mersin, Muş, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Tokat (Eschrich, 1897; Kiritshenko, 1918; Hoberlandt, 1956; Önder et al., 1995; Yılmaz, 1996; Lodos et al., 1978, 1998; Kıyak, 1993; Derjanschi & Péricart, 2005; Dursun & Kartal, 2008c; Kment & Jindra, 2008; Dursun & Fent, 2011b; Gözüaçık et al., 2011; Özgen, 2012; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

Eurydema (Rubrodorsalium) ventralis Kolenati, 1846

Material examined: **Çankırı Prov.:** Ilgaz, Belören, 40°52'11"N, 33°29'39"E, 1543 m, 25.07.2013, ♀, Yuvasaray village exit 4. km from Yukarıöz, 40°52'8"N, 33°46'27"E, 1101 m, 25.VII.2013, 3 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; Korgun, Kayıçivi-Ildızım village road crosroad, 40°42'3"N, 33°28'34"E, 982 m, 22.IV.2013, ♀; Şabanözü, 3. km between Şabanözü-Eldivan road, 40°28'48"N, 33°18'37"E, 1141 m, 24.IV.2013, ♂, 2. km from Çankırı exit to Yapraklı, 40°35'57"N, 33°37'12"E, 730 m, 23.VII.2013, ♀.

Chorotype: Palearctic.

Previous records: Adana, Afyon, Ağrı, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Edirne, Erzincan, Erzurum, Giresun, Hakkâri, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kırıkkale, Kırklareli, Kırşehir, Kütahya, Kocaeli, Konya, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Muş, Niğde, Sakarya, Sinop, Sivas, Şırnak, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Tunceli, Trabzon, Tunceli, Uşak (Horváth, 1883; Eschrich, 1897; Kiritshenko, 1918; Horváth, 1918; Fahringer, 1922; Lodos et al., 1978; Gadeau de Kerville, 1939; Hoberlandt, 1956; Wagner, 1966; Lodos et al., 1978, 1998; Kıyak, 1993; Yılmaz, 1996; Lodos et al., 1998; Fent & Aktaş, 1999; Kıyak, 2000; Derjanschi & Péricart, 2005; Özgen et al., 2005b; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun & Kartal, 2008c; Demirel, 2009; Külekçi et al., 2009; Fent, 2010, 2011; Şerban, 2010; Dursun & Fent, 2011b; Tezcan et al., 2013; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Dirik & Kıvan, 2016; Kıyak, 2016; Orçan & Kıvan, 2017; Çerçi & Gözüaçık, 2019; Tolga & Yoldaş, 2019; Koca & Kütük, 2020; Bulak & Yıldırım, 2021; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

Eysarcoris ventralis (Westwood, 1837)

Material examined: **Çankırı Prov.:** Atkaracalar, Yakalı village entrance, 40°53'56"N, 33°8'51"E, 1210 m, 25.VIII.2013, ♀; Ilgaz, Aşağıdere village entrance, 40°56'31.5"N, 33°38'7.4"E, 945 m, 17.VII.2014, ♀.

Chorotype: Subcosmopolitan.

Previous records: Ağrı, Adana, Adıyaman, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, Isparta, İçel, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kırklareli, Kocaeli, Konya, Manisa, Mardin, Muğla, Muş, Nevşehir, Niğde, Ordu, Osmaniye, Rize, Sakarya, Samsun, Siirt, Sinop, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Şırnak, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Trabzon, Uşak, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883 as *Stollia inconspicua*; Puton & Noualhier, 1895 as *S. inconspicua*; Horváth, 1901 as *S. inconspicua*; Fahringer, 1922 as *S. inconspicua*; Kiritshenko, 1918, 1924 as *S. inconspicua*; Hoberlandt, 1956 as *S. inconspicua*; Wagner, 1966; Lodos et al., 1978,

1998 as *E. inconspicuus*; Önder et al., 1981, 1983, 1984, 1995 as *E. inconspicuus*; Kıyak, 1990 as *E. inconspicuus*; Kıvan, 1998; Fent & Aktaş, 1999; Öz Saraç et al., 2001; Özgen et al., 2005b as *E. inconspicuus*; Dursun & Kartal, 2008a; Karsavuran et al., 2008; Demirel, 2009; Külekçi et al., 2009; Fent, 2010; Şerban, 2010; Dursun & Fent, 2011a; Gözüaçık et al., 2011; Tezcan et al., 2013; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Çıtırık-kaya et al., 2015; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

***Neottiglossa leporina* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1830)**

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Çerkeş, Kabak köy- Çaylı village between 2 km., 40°54'34"N, 32°56'20"E, 1236 m, 25.VIII.2013, ♀.

Chorotype: Asiatic-European.

Previous records: Ankara, Amasya, Bartın, Bolu, Bursa, Çankırı, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzurum, Iğdır, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Kars, Kastamonu, Kırklareli, Muğla, Ordu, Samsun, Sinop, Tokat, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883, 1901; Kiritshenko, 1918; Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1998; Kıyak, 1993; Önder et al., 1995; Fent & Aktaş, 2007; Dursun & Kartal, 2008a; Külekçi et al., 2009; Fent, 2010; Dursun & Fent, 2011a; Tezcan et al., 2013; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

***Palomena prasina* (Linnaeus, 1761)**

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Centre, Dutagaç village, 40°41'25"N, 33°48'56"E, 1030 m, 24.VII.2013, ♀, Yeşilören village E5 highway between, 40°49'38"N, 32°37'57"E, 1154 m, 28.VIII.2013, ♀; Çerkeş, Between Türbaşı and Dağçukurören village, 40°44'39"N, 32°50'14"E, 1271 m, 29.VIII.2013, ♂; Ilgaz, Kırkpınar hingland road, 41°00'18,0"N, 33°39'03,9"E, 1493 m, 17.VII.2014, ♀.

Chorotype: Palearctic.

Previous records: Asian Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bilecik, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Bilecik, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Düzce, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hakkâri, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İçel, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kırklareli, Kocaeli, Konya, Kütahya, Manisa, Mersin, Ordu, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Samsun, Sinop, Sivas, Şırnak, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Trabzon, Tunceli, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883; Puton, 1892; Fahringer, 1922; Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1978, 1998; Kıyak, 1993; Önder et al., 1995; Fent, & Aktaş, 1999; Awad, 2000; Kıyak, 2000, 2016; Özgen et al., 2005a; Dursun & Kartal, 2008b; Külekçi et al., 2009; Fent, 2010; Şerban, 2010; Dursun & Fent, 2011a; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Orçan & Kıvan, 2017; Çerçi & Gözüaçık, 2019; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

***Palomena viridissima* (Poda, 1761)**

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Çerkeş, Karamustafa village entrance, 40°47'6"N, 32°59'2"E, 1164 m, 30.VIII.2013, ♀.

Chorotype: Palearctic.

Previous records: Afyonkarahisar, Ankara, Antalya, Edirne, Giresun, Hatay, İçel, İstanbul, İzmir, Kırklareli, Kütahya, Manisa, Mardin, Ordu, Osmaniye, Sinop (Lodos et al., 1978, 1998; Awad, 2000; Özgen et al., 2005a, b; Dursun & Kartal, 2008b; Dursun & Fent, 2011a; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

***Peribalus (Peribalus) strictus strictus* (Fabricius, 1803)**

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Kurşunlu, Sünürlü-Sakaeli between, 40°42'01"N, 33°08'53"E, 1415 m, 21.V.2014, ♂.

Chorotype: Asiatic-European.

Previous records: Adana, Antalya, Aydın, Bayburt, Burdur, Çanakkale, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Gaziantep, Giresun, Iğdır, İzmir, Karabük, Kastamonu, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Samsun, Sivas, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Zonguldak (Puton & Noualhier, 1895; Hoberlandt, 1956; Önder et al., 1995; Lodos et al., 1998; Fent & Aktaç, 1999; Awad, 2000; Dursun & Kartal, 2008b; Fent, 2010; Şerban, 2010; Tezcan et al., 2010, 2013; Dursun & Fent, 2011a; Matocq et al., 2014; Orçan & Kıvan, 2017; Çerçi et al., 2018; Çerçi & Gözüaçık, 2019; Bulak & Yıldırım, 2021; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

Peribalus (Peribalus) strictus vernalis (Fabricius, 1803)

Material examined: **Çankırı prov.:** Atkaracalar, Yakalı village entrance, 40°53'56"N, 33°8'51"E, 1210 m, 25.VIII.2013, ♀; Bayramören, Dereköy Harmancık between, 41°01'26,5"N, 33°13'28,4"E, 1184 m, 22.VIII.2014, ♂; Centre, Danabaşı village, 40°31'33"N, 34°02'46"E, 724 m, 26.IV.2014, ♀, Eldivan exit-Çankırı between, 2. km 40°34'23"N, 33°30'42"E, 857 m, 26.IV.2014, 3 ♀♀, ♂; Çerkeş, between Dere Plateau - Suluk Plateau, 40°42'44"N, 32°52'56"E, 1422 m, 29.VIII.2013, ♂, Dağçukurören village, 40°44'32"N, 32°50'17"E, 1271 m, 29.VIII.2013, ♂; Ilgaz, Ilgaz exit-Gircen, 40°54'55"N, 33°37'41"E, 887 m, 22.IV.2013, ♀, Yaylaören village distinction, 40°52'42"N, 33°30'31"E, 914 m, 22.IV.2013, ♂; Kızılırmak, Boyacıoğlu Karamürsel between, 40°25'36"N, 34°02'19"E, 543 m, 24.IV.2014, ♂, Karallı Village return 2. km 40°18'30"N, 33°56'36"E, 606 m, 25.IV.2014, ♀, Karamürsel Köyü turnout, 40°26'18"N, 34°01'19"E, 550 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀, 2 ♂♂, Karamürsel village exit Halimintepe, 40°24'06"N, 34°02'26"E, 550 m, 24.IV.2014, ♂, Kuzeykışla Village entrance, 40°22'14"N, 34°03'00"E, 600 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀, 2 ♂♂; Korgun, between Karatekin and Yolkaya village 40°41'30"N, 33°29'20"E, 957 m, 22.IV.2013, ♂, Kayaçivi, 40°41'47,3"N, 33°27'43,5"E, 1005 m, 07.VIII.2014, ♀, ♂; Orta, Elden Village 40°39'22"N, 32°58'21"E, 1446 m, 21.V.2014, ♀.

Chorotype: Palearctic.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Afyonkarahisar, Ağrı, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Batman, Bayburt, Bilecik, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hatay, Iğdır, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kars, Karabük, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırklareli, Kırşehir, Kilis, Kocaeli, Konya, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Niğde, Ordu, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Siirt, Şanlıurfa, Şırnak, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Uşak, Van, Zonguldak (Puton & Noualhier, 1895; Escherich, 1897; Horváth, 1901, 1905; Kiritshenko, 1918; Gadeau de Kerville, 1939; Hoberlandt, 1956; Wagner, 1959; Lodos et al., 1978, 1982, 1998; Önder et al., 1981, 1984; Lodos et al., 1987; Kıyak, 1990; Uygun et al., 1995; Önder et al., 1995, 2006; Kıvan, 1998; Fent & Aktaç, 1999; Awad, 2000; Kıyak, 2000; Öz-saraç et al., 2001; Kıyak et al., 2004; Özgen et al., 2005a, b; Bolu et al., 2006; Kaplan, 2007; Dursun & Kartal, 2008b; Demirel, 2009; Külekçi et al., 2009; Gözüaçık, 2011; Gözüaçık et al., 2011; Özgen, 2012; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Dirik & Kıvan, 2016; Orçan & Kıvan, 2017; Bulak & Yıldırım, 2021 as *H. vernalis*; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

Piezodorus lituratus (Fabricius, 1794)

Material examined: **Çankırı Prov.:** Bayramören, Karakışla village on the road, 40°57'01"N, 33°09'27"E, 916m, 27.VII.2013, ♂; Centre, Balıbağı Plateau, 40°29'50"N, 33°52'42"E, 774 m, 25.IV.2014, ♀, Eldivan exit-Çankırı between, 2. km, 40°34'23"N, 33°30'42"E, 857 m, 26.IV.2014, 5 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂, Hasakça village return, 40°39'59"N, 33°44'28"E, 863 m, 24.VII.2013, ♀; Çerkeş, Coroğlu Village turnout, 40°52'10,7"N, 32°56'58,8"E, 1434 m, 20.VII.2014, ♀, between Yakuplar and Örenkoy, 40° 44'44 " N,

32° 52'25" E, 1301 m, 29.VIII.2013, ♀, Dodurga- Çakmak village between 4. km, 40°57'21"N, 33°1'26"E, 1398 m, 27.VIII.2013, ♀, Doğdu village, 40°53'15,4"N, 32°55'01,3"E, 1559 m, 19.VIII.2014, ♀, Karamustafa Village entrance, 40°47'6"N, 32°59'2"E, 1164 m, 30.VIII.2013, ♂; Ilgaz, Kayı village exit, 40°53'44"N, 33°28'33"E, 1182 m, 22.IV.2013, ♂, Yenidemirciler ile Süleyman Hancılar between, 40°54'48,2"N, 33°30'13,7"E, 983 m, 19.VII.2014, ♀, ♂; Kızılırmak, Aşağıovacık Village entrance, 40°26'29"N, 33°53'27"E, 576 m, 25.IV.2014, ♂, Kenallı-Halaçlı between, 40°18'51,2"N, 33°59'12"E, 565 m, 12.VIII.2014, ♂, Saraycık Village turn out, 40°20'01"N, 33°58'29"E, 565 m, 25.IV.2014, ♀; Korgun, Akçavakıf, 40°41'40"N, 33°33'37"E, 826 m, 22.IV.2013, ♂, Aşağıçavuş village on the Çankırı-Korgun road, 40°41'08"N, 33°36'41"E, 837 m, 21.IV.2013, ♀, 2 ♂♂, Kayaçivi 40°41'47,3"N, 33°27'43,5"E, 1005 m, 07.VIII.2014, 3 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂, Maruf exit, 40°38'25"N, 33°26'02"E, 1200 m, 23.V.2014, ♀, ♂, Maruf Köy exit, 40°38'18"N, 33°26'22"E, 1181 m, 20.V.2014, ♂; Orta, Akcaören-Elmalı between, 40°31'59,2"N, 33°10'43"E, 1197 m, 07.VIII.2014, ♀, 2 ♂♂, Akçaören Village, 40°30'56"N, 33°12'39"E, 1200 m, 23.V.2014, ♀, Çerkeş Hacılar, 40°42'34"N, 32°58'42"E, 1277 m, 21.V.2014, ♂; Şabanözü, Büyükyakalı Village entrance, 40°28'38"N, 33°14'25"E, 1091 m, 23.V.2014, 2 ♀♀, Demirsahan Köy turnout, 40°25'43, 6"N, 33°17'38,1"E, 1035 m, 08.VIII.2014, ♂; Yapraklı, Aşağıöz turnout, 40°48'26,1"N, 33°54'41,6"E, 1144 m, 25.VIII.2014, ♂.

Chorotype: Palearctic.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Ardahan, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bingöl, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Kars, Kastamonu, Kırklareli, Kütahya, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Ordu, Samsun, Sinop, Şanlıurfa, Şırnak, Tekirdağ, Trabzon, Tokat, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883, 1891, 1901; Puton, 189; Kiritshenko, 1918, 1924; Fahringer, 1922; Linnavuori, 1954; Hoberlandt, 1956; Wagner, 1959; Linnavuori, 1965; Lodos et al., 1978, 1989, 1998; Önder et al., 1981, 1983, 1995, 2006; Kıyak, 1990, 1993, 2000; Kıvan, 1998; Fent & Aktaş, 1999; Öz Saraç et al., 2001; Özgen et al., 2005a, b; Bolu et al., 2006; Dursun & Kartal, 2008b, c; Külekçi et al., 2009; Fent, 2010, 2011; Gözüaçık et al., 2011; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Çıtrikkaya et al., 2015; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Özgen & Dioli, 2018; Çerçi & Gözüaçık, 2019; Tolga & Yoldaş, 2019; Bulak & Yıldırım 2021; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

***Staria lunata* (Hahn, 1835)**

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Ilgaz, between Hacıhasan-Sazak 40°57'00,9"N, 33°42'57,8"E, 1134 m, 24.VIII.2014, ♀.

Chorotype: Mediterranean.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bilecik, Bolu, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hatay, İçel, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kars, Kastamonu, Manisa, Mardin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Ordu, Osmaniye, Samsun, Sinop, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Tunceli, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883, 1901, 1919; Puton, 1892; Fahringer, 1922; Hoberlandt, 1956; Wagner, 1959; Linnavuori, 1965; Lodos et al., 1978, 1998; Kıyak, 1993, 2000; Önder et al., 1995; Fent & Aktaş, 1999; Awad, 2000; Dursun & Kartal, 2008b; Fent, 2010; Şerban, 2010; Dursun & Fent, 2011a; Gözüaçık et al., 2011; Tezcan et al., 2013; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Özgen & Dioli, 2018; Çerçi & Özgen 2021; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

***Sciocoris (Sciocoris) cursitans cursitans* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Material examined: **Çankırı Prov.:** Kızılırmak, Kuzey kışla village entrance, 40°22'14"N, 34°03'00"E, 600 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀.

Chorotype: Palearctic.

Previous records: Bayburt, Bilecik, Bolu, Bursa, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Hatay, Isparta, İzmir, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırklareli, Kütahya, Manisa, Muğla, Şanlıurfa, Tekirdağ (Horváth, 1883; Hoberlandt, 1956; Linnavuori, 1965; Lodos et al., 1978, 1998; Lodos & Önder, 1982; Kıyak, 1990; Önder et al., 1995; Fent, 2010; Gözüaçık et al., 2011; Fent, & Japoshvili, 2012; Tezcan et al., 2013; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Fent, & Dursun, 2022).

Sciocoris (Aposciocoris) macrocephalus Fieber, 1851

Material examined: **Çankırı Prov.:** Çankırı, Şabanözü, Şabanözü entrance, 40°30'20,4"N, 33°18'33,9"E, 1148 m, 08.VII.2014, ♀; Kızılırmak, Bozkır village entrance, 40°26'54,3"N, 33°49'25"E, 1637 m, 11.VIII.2014, ♂.

Chorotype: West Palearctic.

Previous records: Adıyaman, Ankara, Antalya, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bilecik, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Gümüşhane, Isparta, İçel, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kars, Kayseri, Kırklareli, Kütahya, Mardin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Niğde, Siirt, Sinop, Sivas, Tekirdağ, Van (Horváth, 1883, 1905; Puntton, 1892; Kiritshenko, 1918; Fahringer, 1922; Linnavuori, 1954; Hoberlandt, 1956; Tuatay et al., 1972; Lodos et al., 1978, 1998; Lodos & Önder, 1982; Önder et al., 1995; Fent & Aktaç, 1999; Derjanschi & Péricart, 2005; Dursun & Kartal, 2008a; Şerban, 2010; Dursun & Fent, 2011b; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021).

Stagonomus amoenus Brullé, 1832

Material examined: **Çankırı Prov.:** Kızılırmak, Kuzey kışla village entrance, 40°22'14"N, 34°03'00"E, 600 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀, Kemalli village entrance, 40°18'6"N, 34°02'37"E, 686 m, 24.IV.2014, ♂.

Chorotype: Turano-Mediterranean.

Previous records: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Balıkesir, Bilecik, Bolu, Bursa, Çanakkale, Düzce, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzurum, Giresun, Hatay, Isparta, İçel, İstanbul, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Karabük, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırklareli, Konya, Ordu, Osmaniye, Samsun, Sinop, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Trabzon, Tunceli, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883, 1905, 1919; Fahringer, 1922; Hoberlandt, 1956; Lodos et al., 1978, 1998; Kıyak, 1990; Fent & Aktaç, 1999; Dursun & Kartal, 2008a; Karşavuran et al., 2008; Fent, 2010; Dursun & Fent, 2011a; Gözüaçık et al., 2011; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Özgen & Dioli, 2018; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

Trochiscocoris hemipterus (Jakovlev, 1879)

Material examined: **Çankırı Prov.:** Şabanözü, between Şabanözü-Karakocaş village, 40°26'48,4"N, 33°21'34,6"E, 928 m, 08.VIII.2014, ♀.

Chorotype: Caucaso Anatolian.

Previous records: Adana, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Karaman, Konya, Nevşehir (Horváth, 1895 as *T. sanguinolentus*; Seidenstücker, 1958 as *T. sanguinolentus*; Lodos et al., 1998 as *T. sanguinolentus* and *T. hemipterus*, Matocq et al., 2014; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021).

Subfamily: Podopinae Amyot & Serville, 1843

Ancyrosoma leucogrammes (Gmelin, 1790)

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Ilgaz, Hacıhasan-Sazak between 40°57'00,9"N, 33°42'57,8"E, 1134 m, 24.VIII.2014, ♀; Kızılırmak, Bozkır village entrance, 40°26'54,3"N, 33°49'25"E, 1637 m, 11.VIII.2014, ♂.

Chorotype: Turano Mediterranean.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bilecik, Burdur, Bursa, Batman, Çanakkale, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, Isparta, İçel, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Konya, Kırklareli, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Sakarya, Siirt, Sinop, Şanlıurfa, Tekirdağ, Tunceli (Horváth, 1883, 1919; Puton, 1892; Kiritshenko, 1918; Fahringer, 1922; Gadeau de Kerville, 1939; Hoberlandt, 1956; Wagner, 1959, 1966; Lodos et al., 1978, 1998; Kıyak, 1990; Önder et al., 1995; Fent & Aktaç, 1999; Öz Saraç et al., 2001; Öz Saraç & Kıyak, 2001; Kıyak et al., 2004; Fent, 2010, 2011; Şerban, 2010; Gözüaçık et al., 2011; Tezcan et al., 2013; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Orçan & Kıvan, 2017; Özgen & Doli, 2018; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Özgen et al., 2021; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

***Graphosoma (Graphosoma) italicum italicum* (O.F. Müller, 1766)**

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: 2. km from Çankırı exit to Yapraklı, 40°35'57"N, 33°37'12"E, 730 m, 23.VII.2013, 2 ♀♀; Atkaracalar, Ilıpınar Village exit, 40°48'10,8"N, 33°05'57,4"E, 1169 m, 20.VIII.2014, 2 ♀♀; Bayramören, between Dere village-Hacılar, 41°01'14,2"N, 33°13'53,9"E, 1081 m, 19.VII.2014, 2 ♀♀, ♂, Karakışla village on the road, 40°57'01"N, 33°09'27"E, 916 m, 27.VII.2013, 2 ♀♀, Yazıören Piriñli between, 40°57'42,2"N, 33°04'48,8"E, 1386 m, 21.VIII.2014, ♀; Centre, between Yukarıçavuş-Dereçatı, 40°44'10,4"N, 33°39'47,3"E, 997 m, 09.VIII.2014, 2 ♀♀, Çankırı Centre, Dutağaç village, 40°41'25"N, 33°48'56"E, 1030 m, 24.VII.2013, ♀; Çerkeş, Akbaş village, 40°53'26" N, 32°49'36"E, 1230 m, 25.VIII.2013, ♂, Provincial borders of Çankırı, Bolu and Ankara, 40°46'46"N, 32°34'19" E, 1709 m, 28.VIII.2013, ♂, Akbaşla Korakoca return, 40°54'55,9"N, 32°53'04,4"E, 912 m, 21.VIII.2014, ♂, Yoncalı village return, 40°42'13"N, 32°46'26"E, 1314 m, 27.VII.2013, ♀; Eldivan, Çiftlik Village entrance, 40°34'35,1"N, 33°30'8,3"E, 856 m, 09.VIII.2014, ♀, Seydiköy, 40°34'38"N, 33°30'26"E, 854 m, 09.VIII.2014, 2 ♂♂; Ilgaz, Beyköy-Saraycık between, 40°59'46,3"N, 33°45'37,4"E, 1211 m, 17.VII.2014, ♀, Eskikıymık köy entry, 41°0'19"N, 33° 41'15" E, 1230 m, 26.VII.2013, 2 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂, Hacıhasan-Sazak between, 40°57'00,9"N, 33°42'57,8"E, 1134 m, 24.VIII.2014, ♀, ♂, İkikavak Village, 40°35'15,6"N, 33°24'33,1"E, 1321 m, 19.VII.2014, 2 ♀♀, Kırkpınar plateau is 3 km., 41°0'25"N, 33°42'28"E, 1252 m, 26.VII.2013, 2 ♀♀, Yenidemirciler-Süleyman Hancılar between, 40°54'48,2"N, 33°30'13,7"E, 983 m, 19.VII.2014, ♂; Kurşunlu, Köpürlü-kapaklı between 40°46'29,2"N, 33°17'25,4"E, 1195 m, 06.VIII.2014, ♂; Şabanözü, Karakocaş-Mart village between, 40°25'20,3"N, 33°21'58"E, 893 m, 08.VIII.2014, ♀; Yapraklı, between Buluca-İğdir, 40°45'32"N, 33°46'58,7"E, 1172 m, 15.VII.2014, ♀, 2 ♂♂.

Chorotype: Asiatic-European.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Ağrı, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Burdur, Bilecik, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Düzce, Edirne, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırklareli, Konya, Kütahya, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Sinop, Sivas, Tunceli, Yalova, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Horváth, 1883, 1901, 1919; Puton & Noualhier, 1895; Escherich, 1897; Kiritshenko, 1918; Fahringer, 1922; Gadeau de Kerville, 1939; Hoberlandt, 1956; Wagner, 1966; Lodos et al., 1978, 1998; Fent & Aktaç, 1999; Kıyak, 1993, 2000; Şerban, 2010; Fent, 2011; Kıyak, 2016; Önder et al., 1995, 2006; Öz Saraç & Kıyak, 2001; Öz Saraç et al., 2001; Külekçi et al., 2009; Fent, 2010; Şerban, 2010; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Yazıcı et al., 2014, Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015;

Orçan & Kivan, 2017; Çerçi & Gözüaçık, 2019; Bulak & Yıldırım, 2021; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

***Graphosoma (Graphosoma) melanoxanthum* Horváth, 1903**

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Şabanözü, between Bakırlı-Karakocaşa, 40°26'53,1"N, 33°21'33,4"E, 942 m, 08.VIII.2014, ♀.

Chorotype: Transcaucasian.

Previous records: Ankara, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzurum, Iğdır, Kars, Yalova (Horváth, 1903, 1908; Kiritshenko, 1918; Hoberlandt, 1956; Seidenstücker, 1975; Lodos et al., 1978; Kıyak, 1990; Külekçi et al., 2009; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

***Graphosoma (Graphosoma) semipunctatum* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Centre, Dutağaç Village, 40°41'25"N, 33°48'56"E, 1030 m, 24.VII.2013, ♀; Çerkeş, Akbaşıla Korakoca dönüşü 40°54'55,9"N, 32°53'04,4"E, 912 m, 21.VIII.2014, ♂.

Chorotype: Mediterranean.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Artvin, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, Iğdır, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırklareli, Konya, Manisa, Mardin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Tekirdağ, Yozgat (Reuter, 1890; Puton, 1892; Horváth, 1903, 1909, 1919; Kiritshenko, 1918; Fahringer, 1922; Hoberlandt, 1956; Linnavuori, 1965; Wagner, 1966; Lodos et al., 1978 as *G. creticum*; Lodos et al., 1998; Önder et al., 1983, 1995 as *G. creticum*; Kıyak 1993; Fent & Aktaç, 1999; Öz Saraç & Kıyak, 2001; Öz Saraç et al., 2001; Kıyak et al., 2004; Bolu et al., 2006; Külekçi et al., 2009; Fent, 2010, 2011; Şerban, 2010; Gözüaçık et al., 2011; Fent; Tezcan et al., 2013; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Orçan & Kivan, 2017; Çerçi & Gözüaçık, 2019; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

DISCUSSION

In this study, a total of 430 Pentatomidae were collected between 2013 and 2014, in order to determine the Pentatomidae fauna of the Çankırı. As result of diagnostic species collected have been identified 30 species and subspecies belonging to the 3 subfamilies. Species recorded from Çankırı belong to 3 subfamilies (Table 1).

Majority of them belong to subfamilies Pentatominae (77%, 403 samples) and Podopinae (16%, 39 samples). Asopinae (7%, 4 samples) was underrepresented in the Heteroptera fauna of Çankırı when compared to Turkish fauna.

Underrepresentation of these families are probably due to methods that we used to collect specimens. *Eurydema (Horvatheurydema) fieberi*, *Palomena viridissima*, *Peribalus (Peribalus) strictus strictus*, *Apodiphus*

amygdali, *Ancyrosoma leucogrammes*, *Antheminia pusio pusio*, *Antheminia varicornis*, *Eysarcoris ventralis*, *Graphosoma (Graphosoma) melanoxanthum*, *Graphosoma (Graphosoma) semipunctatum*, *Sciocoris (Sciocoris) cursitans cursitans*, *Sciocoris (Aposciocoris) macrocephalus*, *Stagonomus amoenus*, *Trochiscocoris hemipterus* and *Picromerus bidens* species are new records for Çankırı province. Additionally, *Antheminia varicornis* (Jakovlev, 1874) is given as the 3rd record from Türkiye.

Türkiye has areas with quite different characteristics, where the four seasons are visible, and the increase in the number of new records and new species belonging to the order Heteroptera will be more clearly revealed day by day. With this study, significant new contributions have been made to the Turkish Pentatomidae fauna.

Table 1. Number of species recorded from Çankırı, sorted into subfamilies of Pentatomidae.

REFERENCES

- Abacıgil, Ö. T., Varlı, S. V., & Tezcan, S., 2010, Edremit (Balıkesir) Körfezi çevresindeki zeytin bahçelerinde kışlak tuzaklarla saptanan Heteroptera türleri 1, *Turkish Journal of Entomology* 34 (1): 105-115.
- Ateş, S., & Kaçar, G., 2021, Sakarya İli Fındık Bahçelerinde Fındık Yeşil Kokarcası (*Palomena prasina* L.) ve Fındık Kurdu (*Curculio nucum* L.)'nun Popülasyon Gelişimleri, *Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam Üniversitesi Tarım ve Doğa Dergisi*, 24 (2): 362-371.
- Aukema, B., & Heijerman, T., 2022, Nieuwe en zeldzame Belgische wantsen uit Bos 't Ename (Hemiptera: Heteroptera), *Bulletin de la Société royale belge d'Entomologie*, 158: 25-36.
- Aukema, B., & Rieger, C., 2006, *Catalogue of Heteroptera of the Palaearctic Region*. Vol. 5. Pentatomomorpha II. Netherlands Entomological Society, Amsterdam, xiv + 550 pp.
- Aukema, B., Rieger, C., & Rabitsch, W., 2013, *Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic Region 6: Supplement*, The Netherlands Entomological Society, Amsterdam, 653 pp.
- Awad, T.I., 2000, *Türkiye Carpocorini (Heteroptera: Pentatomidae: Pentatominae) Türleri Üzerinde Sistemik ve Faunistik Araştırmalar*, Phd Thesis, Ege University, Institute of Natural and Applied Sciences, İzmir/ Bornova, 171 pp.
- Awel, M.M., 1977, *Türkiye'de bulunan önemli Aelia F. (Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) türlerinin taksonomik karakterleri ve bunlardan Ege Bölgesi'nde yaygın olarak bulunan Aelia acuminata L.'nin biyolojisi ve doğal düşmanları üzerinde araştırmalar*, Phd Thesis. Ege University, Institute of Natural and Applied Sciences, İzmir/ Bornova.
- Bolu, H., 2002, Investigations on the fauna of insects and mites in pistachio areas in South Eastern Anatolia Region of Turkey. *Turkish Journal of Entomology*, 26 (3): 197-208.
- Bolu, H., Özgen, İ., & Fent, M., 2006, The Investigations on Almond Pentatomidae (Heteroptera) Fauna in Diyarbakır, Elazığ and Mardin Province, *Yüzüncü Yıl Üniversitesi, Ziraat Fakültesi, Tarım Bilimleri Dergisi*, 16 (1): 25-28.
- Bulak, Y. & Yıldırım, E., 2021, Contribution to the knowledge of Alydidae, Coreidae, Rhopalidae and Pentatomidae (Hemiptera) fauna from fruit orchards in Iğdır Province of Turkey, *Munis Entomology & Zoology*, 16 (2): 947-952.
- Çerçi, B., & Gözüaçık, C., 2019, Contribution to Pentatomidae (Heteroptera) fauna of Iğdır and İstanbul with three new records for Turkish fauna, *Journal of the Heteroptera of Turkey*, 1 (1-2): 33-40.
- Çerçi, B., & Özgen, İ., 2021, Contribution to the knowledge of Heteroptera (Hemiptera)

- fauna of Elazığ province with a new record for the fauna of Turkey, *Journal of the Heteroptera of Turkey*, 3 (1): 50-75.
- Çerçi, B., Özgen, İ., & Dioli, P., 2018, Additional faunistic notes on Heteroptera (Hemiptera: Insecta) in East Anatolia (Turkey). *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies*, 6 (1): 1225-1231.
- Çıtırkkaya, B., Fent, M., Tezcan, S., & Gülperçin, N., 2015, Heteroptera species (Hemiptera) collected by pheromone traps of *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus* (Olivier 1790) (Coleoptera: Dryophthoridae) in İzmir province of Turkey, *Entomofauna Zeitschrift für Entomologie*, 36 (14): 201- 208.
- Demirel, N., 2009, Determination of Heteroptera species on canola plants in Hatay province of Turkey, *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 4 (11): 1226-1233.
- Derjanschi, V.V., & Péricart, J., 2005, Hémiptérés Pentatomoidea euro - méditerranéens 1. Généralités. Systématique: Première Partie, *Faune de France*, 90: 1-494.
- Dirik, E., & Kıvan, M., 2016, Edirne ili buğday ekiliş alanlarında tespit edilen Heteroptera türleri, *Türkiye Entomoloji Bülteni*, 6 (4): 357-369.
- Dursun, A., 2004, *A Faunistic and Taxonomic Study on the Pentatomidae Heteroptera Species of Middle Black Sea Region of Turkey*, Phd Thesis. Ondokuz Mayıs University, Institute of Natural and Applied Sciences, Biology Main Division, Samsun-Turkey, 176 pp.
- Dursun, A., & Fent, M., 2011a, Additional records on the Halyini, Carpocorini, Aeliini and Eysarcorini (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae: Pentatominae) of the Kelkit Valley, Turkey, *Biharian Biologist*, 5 (2): 151-156.
- Dursun, A., & Fent, M., 2011b, Kelkit Vadisi Sciocorini Amyot & Serville, 1843 ve Strachiini Mulsant & Rey, 1866 (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae: Pentatominae) faunası üzerine çalışmalar, *Türkiye Entomoloji Bülteni*, 1 (3): 181-188.
- Dursun, A., & Kartal, V., 2008a, Orta Karadeniz Bölgesi Halyini Amyot & Serville, 1843, Sciocorini Amyot & Serville, 1843, Aeliini Douglas & Scott, 1865 ve Eysarcorini Mulsant & Rey, 1866 (Heteroptera: Pentatomidae: Pentatominae) türleri üzerine faunistik bir araştırma, *Turkish Journal of Entomology*, 32 (4): 303-315.
- Dursun, A., & Kartal, V., 2008b, Orta Karadeniz Bölgesi Strachiini Mulsant & Rey, 1866, Pentatomini Leach, 1815 ve Piezodorini Atkinson, 1888 (Heteroptera: Pentatomidae: Pentatominae) türleri üzerine faunistik bir araştırma, *Turkish Journal of Entomology*, 32 (3): 225-239.
- Dursun, A., & Kartal, V., 2008c, Orta Karadeniz Bölgesi Carpocorini Stål, 1876 (Heteroptera: Pentatomidae: Pentatominae) türleri üzerine faunistik bir araştırma, *Turkish Journal of Entomology*, 32 (1): 43-59.
- Escherich, K., 1897, Beitrag zur Hemipterenfauna Kleinasien, *Entomologische Nachrichten*, 23: 124-127.
- Fahringer, J., 1922. Eine Rhynchotenausbeute aus der Türkei, Kleinasien und benachbarten Gebieten. *Konowia*, 1: 137-144.
- Fent, M., 2010, Contributions to Pentatomoidea (Heteroptera) fauna of Western Black Sea Region with a new record for Anatolian fauna: *Neottiglossa lineolata* (Mulsant & Rey, 1852), *Journal of the Entomological Research Society*, 12 (1): 53-65.
- Fent, M., 2011, Gökçeada ve Bozcaada Heteroptera (Insecta: Hemiptera) Faunasına Katkıları, *Trakya University Journal of Science*, 12 (1): 35-46.
- Fent, M., & Aktaş, N., 1999, Edirne Yöresi Pentatomidae (Heteroptera) Faunası Üzerine Taksonomik ve Faunistik Araştırmalar, *Turkish Journal of Zoology*, 23 (2): 377-395.
- Fent, M., & Aktaş, N., 2007, New records of the Pentatomoidea (Heteroptera) fauna for Europe. *Turkey and the Turkish Thrace. Entomological News*, 118 (4): 336-349.
- Fent, M., & Aktaş, N., 2008, Anmerkungen zu einigen im Adultstadium Überwinternden Heteropteren und ihrer Überwinterungsplätze in der Türkischen Provinz Edirne, *Heteropteron*, 28: 11-15.
- Fent, M., & Dursun, A., 2022, An up-to-date checklist of Turkish Pentatomidae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) with additional records, *Trakya University Journal of Natural Sciences*, 23 (Special Issue: Biodiversity of Insect): 65-111.
- Fent, M., Dursun, A., Karsavuran, Y., Tezcan, S., & Demirözer, O., 2010, A review of the tribe Halyini in Turkey (Hemiptera:

- Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) with two new records: *Apodiphus integriceps* and *Mustha vicina*, *Journal of the Entomological Research Society*, 12 (2): 1-13.
- Fent, M., & Japoshvili, G., 2012, Heteroptera (Hemiptera) Fauna of Isparta-Gölcük Natural Park with some rare and peculiar species and new records for Mediterranean Region of Turkey, *Türkiye Entomoloji Bülteni*, 2 (3): 149-163.
- Gadeau De Kerville, H., 1939, *Voyage zoologique d'Henri Gadeu de Kerville en Asie Mineure* (April-Mai 1912), Paul Le Chevalier, Paris, 148 pp.
- Ghauri, M.S.K., 1977, A revision of *Apodiphus spinola* (Heteroptera: Pentatomidae), *Bulletin of Entomological Research*, 67: 97-106.
- Gözüaçık, C., Fent, M., & Özgen, İ., 2011, Güneydoğu Anadolu Bölgesi Pentatomidae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) faunasına katkılar, *Türkiye entomoloji bülteni*, 1 (4): 235-252.
- Henry, T.J., 2017, *Biodiversity of Heteroptera*, In: Foottit, R. G. & Adler, P. H. (eds): *Insect Biodiversity. Science and Society*. Vol. I. Second edition. Wiley-Blackwell, Oxford, 904 pp.
- Hoberlandt, L., 1956, Results of the zoological scientific expedition of the National Museum in Praha to Turkey, 18. Hemiptera IV. terrestrial Hemiptera-Heteroptera of Turkey, *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae*, 3: 1-264.
- Horváth, G., 1883, Heteroptera Anatolica in regione Brussae collecta enumeravit, *Természetráji Füzetek*, 7: 21- 30.
- Horváth, G., 1891, Hémiptères recueillis dans l'Arménie russe avec la description d'espèces et variétés nouvelles, *Revue d'Entomologie*, 10 (3): 68-79.
- Horváth, G., 1901, Hémiptères du voyage de M. Martinez Escalera dans l'Asie-Mineure, *Természetráji Füzetek*, 24: 469-485.
- Horváth, G., 1903, Conspectus specierum generis *Graphosoma*. *Annales Musei Nationalis Hungarici*, 1: 345-354.
- Horváth, G., 1905, Ergebnisse einer naturwissenschaftlichen Reise zum Erdschias-Dagh (Kleinasien) ausgeführt von Dr. Arnold Penther und Dr. Emerich Zederbauer, Hemipteren, *Annalen des Naturhistorischen Hofmuseums Wien*, 20: 179-189.
- Horváth, G., 1909, Les *Graphosoma* d'Europe, *Annales Historico-Naturales Musei Nationalis Hungarici*, 7: 143-150.
- Horváth, G., 1918, Ad cognitionem faunae hemipterorum balcanicae, *Annales Historico-Naturales Musei Nationalis Hungarici*, 16: 321-340.
- Horváth, G., 1919, Ergebnisse einer mit Unterstützung der Kais. Akademie der Wissenschaften in Wien ausgeführten zoologischen Forschungsreise von weiland Prof. Dr. Franz Tölg nach Kleinasien (Amanus Gebirge).V. *Rhynchota*, *Archiv Naturgeschichte*, 85: 146-147.
- Kaçar, G., & Dursun, A., 2015, Survey and abundance of Suborder Heteroptera: Pest and beneficial species in olive groves of Turkey, *Egyptian Journal of Biological Pest Control*, 25 (2): 499-502.
- Kaplan, M., 2007, *The investigations on the determine of insect and acari species and their natural enemies in the strawberry fields in Elazığ province*, Master thesis, Harran University Publications, Şanlıurfa, 67 p.
- Karsavuran, Y., Demirözer, O., Aslan, B., & Karaca, İ., 2008, Faunistic studies on Pentatomidae and Scutellaridae families belonging to Heteroptera order in the region of Isparta, Turkey, *Journal of Entomology*, 5 (3): 213-217.
- Kıvan, M., 1998, *Eurygaster integriceps* Put. (Heteroptera: Scutelleridae)'nin yumurta parazitoiti *Trissolcus semistriatus* Nees (Hymenoptera: Scelionidae)'un biyolojisi üzerinde araştırmalar, *Turkish Journal of Entomology*, 22 (4): 243-257.
- Kıvan, M., & Dirik, E., 2016, Edirne ili buğday ekiliş alanlarında tespit edilen Heteroptera türleri. *Türkiye Entomoloji Bülteni*, 6 (4): 357-369.
- Kıyak, S., 1990, Systematisch-Ökologische Untersuchungen über die Wanzen (Insecta: Heteroptera) Aus dem Gebiet Hazar-See, Maden und Ergani (Prov. Elazığ)-II, *Gazi Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Dergisi*, 1: 97-144.
- Kıyak, S., 1993, Über terrestrische Wanzenarten von Soğuksu Nationalpark, Ankara, Türkei, *Priamus*, 6 (3/4): 131-156.
- Kıyak, S., 2000, Işık Dağı ve çevresinde yaşayan Heteroptera (Insecta) türlerinin faunistik, sistematik ve ekolojik yönden araştırılması

- II, *Gazi Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 13 (2): 347-367.
- Kıyak, S., 2016, On Heteroptera fauna of Binboğa Mountains (Turkey, Kahramanmaraş-Kayseri), *Munis Entomology & Zoology*, 11 (2): 441-449.
- Kıyak, S., Öz Saraç, Ö., & Salur, A., 2004, Additional notes on the Heteroptera fauna of Nevşehir Province (Turkey), *Gazi University Journal of Science*, 17 (1): 21-29.
- Kiritshenko, A.N., 1918, Hemiptera-Heteroptera faunae Caucasicae. Pars I., *Memories Museum Caucase*, 6: 1-177.
- Kiritshenko, A.N., 1924, Beitrag zur Hemipterenfauna des südlichen Armenien, *Wiener Entomologische Zeitung*, 41: 1-5.
- Kment, P., & Jindra, Z., 2008, New records of *Eurydema fieberi* from the Czech Republic with corrections to some previously published records of Palaearctic *Eurydema* species (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae), *Acta Musei Moraviae Scientiae biologicae* (Brno), 93: 11-27.
- Koca, A.S., & Kütük, H., 2020, Pests, beneficial insect species and their bio-ecologies in the collar gardens of düzce province of Turkey, *Bitki Koruma Bülteni*, 60 (4): 13-20.
- Küçükbasımacı, İ., & Kıyak, S., 2015, A study on the fauna of Heteroptera of Ilgaz Mountains (Kastamonu, Çankırı) with a new record for Turkey, *Nevşehir Bilim ve Teknoloji Dergisi*, 4 (1): 1-33.
- Külekcı, G., Yıldırım, E., & Tezcan, S., 2009, Contribution to the knowledge of the Pentatomidae (Heteroptera) fauna of Turkey, *Linzer biologische Beiträge*, 41(1): 697-708.
- Linnavuori, R., 1954, A Palaearctic Heteropterous material collected by J. Sahlberg and U. Saalas, *Annales Entomologici Fennici*, 19: 147-167.
- Linnavuori, R., 1965, Studies on the South- and Eastmediterranean Hemipterous Fauna. III. Hemipterological observations from Turkey, *Acta Entomologica Fennica*, 21: 45-47.
- Lodos, N., & Önder, F., 1983, Contribution to the study on the Turkish Pentatomoidea (Heteroptera) VI. Asopinae (Amyot & Serville, 1843), *Türkiye Bitki Koruma Dergisi*, 7 (4): 221-230.
- Lodos, N., Önder, F., Pehlivan, E., & Atalay, R., 1978, *Ege ve Marmara Bölgesi'nin zararlı böcek faunasının tespiti üzerinde çalışmalar* [(Curculionidae, Scarabaeidae (Coleoptera), Pentatomidae, Lygaeidae, Miridae (Heteroptera)], T.C. Gıda-Tarım ve Hayvancılık Bakanlığı Zirai Mücadele ve Zirai Karantina Genel Müdürlüğü, 135-169.
- Lodos, N., Önder, F., Pehlivan, E., Atalay, R., Erkin, E., Karsavuran, Y., Tezcan, S., & Aksoy, S., 1998, *Faunistic Studies on Pentatomoidea (Plataspidae, Acanthosomatidae, Cydnidae, Scutelleridae, Pentatomidae) of Western Black Sea, Central Anatolia and Mediterranean Regions of Turkey*, Ege Üniversitesi Bornova-İzmir, 75 pp.
- Lodos, N., Önder, F., Pehlivan, E., Atalay, R., Erkin, E., Karsavuran, Y., & Tezcan, S., 1989, Akdeniz Bölgesi'nin ziraatta zararlı ve faydalı böcek faunasının tespiti üzerinde araştırmalar (Curculionidae, Scarabaeidae (Coleoptera), Plataspidae, Cydnidae, Acanthosomatidae, Scutelleridae, Pentatomidae, Lygaeidae, Miridae (Heteroptera)), *Doğa Türk Tarım ve Ormanlık Dergisi*, 13 (1): 81-88.
- Lodos, N., Önder, F., Pehlivan, E., Atalay, R., Erkin, E., Karsavuran, Y., & Tezcan, S., 1987, Akdeniz Bölgesi'nin Ziraatta zararlı ve faydalı böcek faunasının tespiti üzerinde araştırmalar, TOAG/502 numaralı basılmamış proje.
- Matocq, A., Sigwalt, D. P., & Özgen, İ., 2014, Terrestrial Hemiptera (Heteroptera) Collected IN South-East Anatolia (Diyarbakır, Mardin and Elazığ Provinces) (Turkey): Second list, *Munis Entomology & Zoology*, 9 (2): 884-930.
- Orçan, S. Ö., & Kıvanç, M., 2017, Pentatomidae (Hemiptera) species on fruit trees in Saray district of Tekirdağ, Turkey, *Global Journal of Advanced Research*, 4 (10): 293-300.
- Önder, F., & Adıguzel, N., 1979, Some Heteroptera collected by light trap in Diyarbakır (Turkey), *Türkiye Bitki Koruma Dergisi*, 3 (1): 25-34.
- Önder, F., Atalay, R., & Karsavuran, Y., 1983, İzmir ili ve çevresinde kışı ergin halde geçen Heteroptera Türleri ve Kışlak Yerleri üzerinde araştırmalar II. Lygaeoidea, Pentatomidae, *Türkiye Bitki Koruma Dergisi*, 7: 129-144.
- Önder, F., Karsavuran, Y., Pehlivan, E., & Turanlı,

- F., 1995, *Güneydoğu Anadolu Projesi (GAP) uygulama alanında saptanan Pentatomoidea (Heteroptera) türleriyle ilgili bir değerlendirme*, GAP Bölgesi Bitki Koruma Sorunları ve Çözüm Önerileri Sempozyumu, 27-29 Nisan, Şanlıurfa, Türkiye, 120-130.
- Önder, F., Karsavuran, Y., Tezcan, S., & Fent, M., 2006, *Heteroptera (Insecta) Catalogue of Turkey*, İzmir, Turkey, 164 pp.
- Önder, F., Ünal, A., & Ünal, E., 1981, Heteroptera fauna collected by light traps in some districts of Northwestern part of Anatolia. *Türkiye Bitki Koruma Dergisi*, 5 (3): 151-169.
- Önder, F., Ünal, A., & Ünal, E., 1984, Heteropterous insects collected by light traps in Edirne, *Türkiye Bitki Koruma Dergisi*, 8 (4): 215-224.
- Özgen, İ., 2012, The species of suborder Heteroptera (Hemiptera) on vineyards agroecosystem which is found in Diyarbakır, Elazığ and Mardin provinces, *Munis Ent & Zool.*, 7 (1): 255-258.
- Özgen, İ., & Dioli, P., 2018, Additional faunistic notes on Pentatomidae and Scutelleridae (Heteroptera) in Bingöl, Elazığ and Tunceli province (Turkey), *International Journal of Fauna and Biological Studies*, 5 (5): 24-26.
- Özgen, İ., Dioli, P., & Çerçi, B., 2021, Additional notes on Heteroptera (Hemiptera) of Eastern Turkey, *International Journal of Fauna and Biological Studies*, 8 (1): 1-4.
- Özgen, İ., Gözüaçık, C., Karsavuran, Y., & Fent, M., 2005a, Güneydoğu Anadolu Bölgesi buğday alanlarında bulunan Pentatomidae (Heteroptera) familyasına ait türler üzerinde araştırmalar, *Türkiye Entomoloji Dergisi*, 29 (1): 61-68.
- Özgen, İ., Gözüaçık, C., Karsavuran, Y., & Fent, M., 2005b, Doğu ve Güneydoğu Anadolu Bölgesi'nde antepfıstığı, kayısı, kiraz ve zeytin ağaçlarında bulunan Pentatomidae (Heteroptera) familyasına ait türlerin saptanması üzerinde çalışmalar, *Ege Üniversitesi Ziraat Fakültesi Dergisi*, 42: 35-43.
- Özsaraç, Ö., & Kiyak, S., 2001, A study on the Heteroptera fauna of Bozcaada (Çanakkale Province), *Journal of Zoology*, 25: 313-322.
- Özsaraç, H., Kiyak, S., & Özsaraç, Ö., 2001, A Study on the Fauna of Heteroptera of Gökçeada (Çanakkale)-II, *Journal of the Institute of Science and Technology of Gazi University*, 14 (4): 1167-1182.
- Puton, A., 1892, Hémiptères nouveaux ou peu connus et notes divers. IV. Hémiptères d'Akbes. Region de l'Amanus (Syrie septentrionale). Récoltés par M. Delagrange, *Revue d'Entomologie*, 11: 24-36.
- Puton, A., & Noualhier, M., 1895, Supplement a la liste des Hémiptères d'Akbes, *Revue d'Entomologie*, 14: 170-177.
- Reuter, O.M., 1890, Notes géographiques sur les Heteropteres palearctiques, *Revue d'Entomologie*, 9: 237-245.
- Rider, D.A., Schwertner, C.F., Vilimová, J., Rédei, D., Kment, P., & Thomas, D.B., 2018, *Higher Systematics of the Pentatomoidea*. pp. 25-201. In: J. E. McPherson (ed.), *Invasive Stink Bugs and Related Species (Pentatomoidea): Biology, Higher Systematics, Semiochemistry, and Management*, *American Entomologist*, 64 (3): 819.
- Rider, D.A., 2002, Stink Bugs. Family Pentatomidae, http://www.brisbaneinsects.com/brisbane_stinkbugs/Pentatomidae.htm
- Seidenstücker, G., 1958, Heteroptera aus Anatolien II, *Istanbul Üniversitesi Fen Fakültesi Mecmuası*, 23: 119-129
- Seidenstücker, G., 1975, Über anatolischen Schildwanzen, *Reichenbachia*, 15: 259-268.
- Şerban, C., 2010, Faunistic data on some true bugs [sic!] species (Insecta: Heteroptera) from West Turkey. [Results of the "Taurus" - 2005 and "Focida" - 2006 expeditions], *Travaux du Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle „Grigore Antipa"*, 53: 171-180.
- Tezcan, S., Gülperçin, N., & Fent, M., 2010, Contribution to the knowledge of the light trap collected Heteroptera fauna occurring in cherry orchards in western Turkey, *Linzer biologische Beiträge*, 42 (1): 817-823.
- Tezcan, S., Gülperçin, N., & Fent, M., 2013, Aspat (Strobilos) antik kenti ve çevresindeki (Bodrum, Muğla) tarım teraslarının Scutelleridae, Cydnidae ve Pentatomidae (Hemiptera: Pentatomoidea) faunası üzerinde bir analiz, *Turkish Journal of Entomology*, 37 (2): 249-259.
- Tolga, M.F., & Yoldaş, Z., 2019, Hemiptera species determined in almond orchards in Mugla and Manisa provinces of Turkey and population fluctuation of *Monosteira*

- unicostata* (Hemiptera: Tingidae), *Akademik Ziraat Dergisi*, 8 (2): 209-216.
- Tuatay, N., Kalkandelen, A., & Aysev, N., 1972, *Nebat Koruma Müzesi Böcek Kataloğu* (1961-1971), T.C. Tarım Bakanlığı Ziraai Mücadele ve Ziraî Karantina Genel Müdürlüğü Yayınları, Ankara, 119 pp.
- Tuncer, C., & Saruhan, İ., 2001, Bazı önemli fındık zararlılarının Samsun ilindeki popülasyon değişimi ve yoğunluğu Üzerine araştırmalar, *OMU Ziraat Fak. Dergisi*, 16 (1): 56-63.
- Uygun, N., Başpınar, H., Şekeroğlu, E., Kornoşor, S., Özgür, A. F., Karaca, G., Ulusoy, M. R., & Kazak, C., 1995, *The investigations on pest and natural enemies that fundamental approaches to the plant protection politica in GAP region of Turkey*, Plant Protection Problems and Solve Suggestions about GAP Region of Turkey, Şanlıurfa, 99-119, 435 p.
- Wagner, E., 1959, Beitrag zur Heteropterenfauna Anatoliens, *Zeitschrift für Angewandte Entomologie*, 44: 102-113.
- Wagner, E., 1966, Eine Heteropterenausbeute aus der Türkei (Hemiptera, Heteroptera), *Bulletin Recherches Agronomiques Gembloux*, 1: 647-654.
- Yazıcı, G., Yıldırım, E., & Moulet, P., 2014, Contribution to the knowledge of the Pentatomidae and Plataspidae (Hemiptera, Heteroptera, Pentatomomorpha) fauna of Entomology and Zoology Studies Turkey, *Linzer biologische Beiträge*, 46 (2): 1819-1842.
- Yazıcı, G., 2022, List of Pentatomomorpha (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) Described by Foreign Scientists in Nazife Tuatay Plant Protection Museum from Turkey. Part I., *Transactions of the American Entomological Society*, 148 (2): 253-264.
- Yılmaz, F., 1996, *Türkiye'de Eurydema Lap. (Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) Türleri Üzerinde Sistematik Araştırmalar*, Phd Thesis, Ege University, Institute of Natural and Applied Sciences, 80 pp.